

GENDER ROLES OF MEN AND WOMEN IN FAMILY RELATIONS

Nurullaeva Kamola

2nd year Master student of SamSIFL

As mentioned in the first chapter of the dissertation, A.V. Kirilina considers gender to be a social model of women and men, determining their social roles and norms of behavior in a particular society [3, p. 20-21]. It follows that the family is an important indicator of gender roles and intra-family relations between men and women.

The group of phraseological units reflecting family (kinship) relations includes units that reveal the national and cultural characteristics of marriage, family, clan and kinship relations within the English linguoculture [5, p. 96].

The conceptual sphere and the linguistic picture of the world are very close to each other objects of thinking. The concept sphere of "kinship relations" is reflected in linguistic units with kinship terms that convey information about the types of kinship.

The study of phraseological units with kinship terms allowed us to divide kinship relations into two main groups:

- 1) blood relations and close family relations;
- 2) distant family relations, including clan ties.

Thus, phraseological semantics made it possible to create a gradation of the degree of kinship within kinship relations. The gradation in this study is based on the classification of Yu.I. Levin, who distinguishes blood and non-blood kinship [5, p. 97].

A family in English linguoculture is represented as two parents and their children living under the same roof. English phraseology is overflowing with

units containing the lexeme family: *happy family*; *family tree*; *a family joke*; *first families* – (amer.) the first settlers, aristocratic circles. Turnover *fresh blood* – denotes new family members, indicating blood relationship. The degree of kinship can be traced in the English proverb *Blood is thicker than water* – blood is not water, its shirt is closer to the body.

In the system of kinship terminology, the lexemes mother "mother" and father "father" are the reference ones. The terms "mother" and "father" are idealized images with the apex sign of gender [2, p. 90].

The image of the father is represented by an older and wise man, the head of the family, from whom the son / daughter receives advice, help and support.

The dictionary definition of the lexeme father "father" is as follows: father – 1) father, parent; 2) ancestor, ancestor, progenitor; 3) oldest member; 4) patron, intercessor, "native father", 5) creator, creator, inspirer; 6) spiritual father, bishop [1, p. 263].

Phraseological units with this component play an important role in the characterization of family and family relations: *like father, like son* – the apple does not fall far from the apple tree; *by (or on) the father's (or paternal) side* – on the paternal side.

The father component can nominate abstract concepts and not indicate consanguinity: *city fathers* – members of the city administration; *Father Christmas* – Santa Claus, Christmas grandfather; *father confessor* – confessor; *Father Superior* – abbot; *founding father* – founder; *Father Time* – time; *the child is father of the man* – the features of an adult are already embedded in the child [4, p. 163].

The father's image also conveys the age of an older member of a society: *father of the chapel* – foreman of printing workers; *the Father of the City* – the oldest alderman of London; *the Father of the House* – the oldest member of the House of Commons; *the Father of the Senate* – (amer.) the oldest senator [4, p. 314].

In colloquial speech, a joking expression with this component is popular: *is your father a glazier?* – you are not transparent, it is said to a person blocking something.

In English phraseology, only one expression with the lexeme "grandfather" was found, which does not indicate a blood relationship: *grandfather clock* – high antique clock.

As the basis of the analysis, we take the dictionary definition of the lexeme “mother”: 1) a female parent of a child or animal; 2) the cause and origin [1, p. 694]. The semantics of the mother lexeme is determined by the following dictionary definition: 1) mother; 2) the beginning, the source of life; 3) incubator, brooder.

In English, there are a large number of expressions with the mother (mummy) component, sometimes without realizing its direct meaning: *Mother country* – Homeland, fatherland; *Mother earth* – Motherland; *mother of pearl*; *the Mother of Presidents* – (amer.) "homeland of presidents", "mother of all states" (nickname of the state of Virginia) (7 of the first 12 American presidents were from the state of Virginia); *mother Superior* – abbess; *mother's mark* – birthmark, mole; *mother tongue* – native language; *mother Bunch* – fortune teller (named after an English fortune teller of the 16th century); *beat somebody to a mummy* – beat someone badly, beat them to death [4, p. 637].

The proverb *Love is the mother of love* – love generates reciprocal love shows the inextricable link between motherhood and the feeling of love.

Dictionary definition of the lexeme “son”: 1) son; 2) son (in circulation); 3) native, descendant [1, p. 666].

Most phraseological expressions with the “son” component have a positive or neutral coloring: *he is a true son of his father, he is his father's own son* – he is the spitting image of the father; *favorite son* – (amer. a politician who enjoys authority in his state; *native son* – the son of his homeland, a local native; *son and heir* – the eldest son; *son (or daughter) of the soil* – a native, a peasant; *a son of*

toil – a worker [4, p. 851].

In the process of analyzing English phraseological units with the lexeme "son", the following negatively colored turns were revealed: *son of a bitch* – (rude) scoundrel; *son of shame* – illegitimate son; *the prodigal son* – (bibl.) prodigal son.

The phraseology of *the sons of men* means "the human race". Some turns with this component indicate professional employment: *a son of Mars* military; a son of Neptune – sailor; *a son of Muses* – poet.

Let us turn to the dictionary interpretation of the lexeme "daughter": 1) daughter; 2) branch, related to [1, p. 182].

The component "daughter" in a number of expressions is presented with a negative coloring. The negative connotation of the lexeme "daughter" is especially pronounced in biblical phraseological units: *the daughter of Jezebel* is a criminal, brazen woman; *the daughter of the horse-leech* is an insatiable extortionist, a bloodsucker. The English expression *Eve's daughter / the daughter of Eve* – Eve's daughter, a representative of the fair sex has a positive assessment.

There are also neutrally colored phraseological units with this component that have nothing to do with kinship relations: *the daughter of soil* – a native, peasant woman; *the gunner's daughter* – the cannon to which the punished sailor was tied; *kiss the gunner's daughter* – to be flogged while being tied to the breech of a cannon; *skipper's daughters* – high waves with white cross; *the Scavenger's daughter* – (hist.) vise, an instrument of torture. An interesting phraseological unit containing three gender-marked components at once, but not denoting either a man or a woman: *the Duke of Exeter's daughter* – (hist.) rack (instrument of torture) [4, p. 230].

The relationship between siblings in an English family is connected by strong blood ties. The word "brother" has the following meaning: 1) brother; 2) fellow, colleague [1, p. 96].

The degree of consanguinity is suggested by the semantics of

phraseological units *full brother* – a brother; *brother german* – a brother; *sworn brothers* – named brothers, twin brothers; *uterine brother* – a half-brother [4, p. 123].

The lexeme “brother” in the structure of many phraseological units indicates not only kinship, but also a friendly attitude or the same professional activity: *brother chip* – a comrade in profession; *brother of the angle* – a fishing companion; *brother of the brush* – a brush companion (artist); *brother of the quill* – a pen companion (writer); *brother at arms* – a fellow in arms [4, p. 122].

The phraseology *brother Jonathan* is a playful nickname of Americans or the US government.

The lexeme “sister” means: 1) a sister; 2) a senior nurse, a nurse; 3) a different girl (as an appeal); 4) a member of a religious community; a nun; 5) related, paired, financially and organizationally related (about the company) [1, p. 653].

The degree of consanguinity is expressed in the phraseological units *full sister* – whole sister; *german sister* – sister; *half sister* – sister only by one of the parents.

The meaning of "a member of a religious community; a nun" is reflected in the turnover *sister of mercy*.

The component “sister” is found in English phraseological units with the most diverse semantics without indication of consanguinity: *Sister Ann* – a faithful female friend; *The Seven Sisters* (or *stars*) - Pleiades (a group of seven stars in the constellation Taurus); *the weird sisters* – witches in Shakespeare's tragedy "Macbeth"; *sister ships* – the same type of ship [1, p. 653].

As can be seen from the examples, the terminology of kinship is a unique lexical layer of the language that distributes the gender roles of men and women within the family.

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